

Features of regulation on the Kazakh common law of the contractual relations arising from civil turns

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Abstract. This article discusses some features of the emergence and development of the legal system of the traditional Kazakh society. Namely, a focus on issues relating to regulation of the features on the Kazakh customary law of contractual relations arising from civil revolutions. A brief description of these types of contracts, as a contract debt sale, barter, donation contract, contract of storage.

Key words: Custom, tradition, the contract, right howling system, institute of donation, the contract of purchase and sale, norm of a common law

The development of the traditional Kazakh society and legal system is based on the specific facts. Traditional Kazakh provisions of the contract on the basis of a wide range of issues, including the scope, scale is a phenomenon. Provisions of the agreement, its development, the formation of different.

Eurasia in Western Siberia and Central Asia XI – XII centuries, the tribe tribal communities at the integration of the Kazakh people, XV century ended with the establishment of the Kazakh Khanate. The same location in space on the basis of spirituality and ethical principles of the Turkish ethnic minority language culture, there was a fortress, which has a special place in the Kazakh customary law. Long path of development of the Kazakh customary law was influenced by many factors, including a special place in the spiritual and ethical principles. Kazakh Society contributed to the development of the steppe nomadic way of life. It is a society of tolerance and Kazakh political and social insisted on the principle that was the basis for the formation of the economic life of the spirit. Of these, each member of a nomadic life on the basis of justice, hospitality, volunteer and respect for elders, as well as peace-loving, trying to help each other and formed such qualities. All other legal systems, applied at the discretion of the Kazakh customs differ. Treated under the conditions of life of the Kazakh people

living traditions reflect the views of the general population the right to legal, unanimously carried out in compliance with it for many centuries. Kazakh traditional customary right of property, is reflected in the ability to change depending on the stream of life. At the same time, the academician S. Zimanov writes: "Kazakh law, which was held in the vast steppes of Kazakhstan, in spite of all the changes and revolutions in the form of the first sürgiştigi, a legal system based on a person's voluntary, that is true freedom of man and mankind is explained by the fact correspond to the constant striving for spiritual ideals and principles. This is a usurper of the rights of Kazakh qanjaldarı and their modes to be determined first of all, one of the reasons" [1, 38 p.]

Kazakh steppes domestic production and exchange of goods and services is determined by the need to meet the need for real-patriarchal nature of the Kazakh ritual contributed to the formation of the contractual rights norms. Any company, regardless of its level of economic development of commodity exchange, material and methods of regulation of relations in the framework of the acquisition of the product and can not exist. Of the agreements signed between the members of the congregation, which is related to different aspects of life, based on the principle of high spirituality. Disputes related to the violation of the obligation of judges made on the basis of the decisions issued by the ritual law, more wisely, fairly different.

XVI century Kasim Khan Kaska Zholy, not the full amount of our time, but the historical documents preserved fragments of the last century Kazakh educators and Russian researchers have to reset it to a certain extent. Scientists to identify the contents of these documents, Kazakh society to obtain information related to the settlement of certain contractual relations. Erkin Abel Kasim Khan's Kaska Zholy have five parts and customs of homogeneity to be codified. One of them, purchase and sale, exchange, loan, Conditions, as well as giving an overview of the rules in connection with the execution of certain types of contracts and is part of the settlement of the liability relations. This feature of the Contractual relations, patriarchal and true relations appear in a certain social relations in the society because qawımaralıq and their relations are regulated in [2, p. 100].

Kazakh customs agreement in the right's traditional Kazakh society centuries-old practice, developing, is one of the established channels. Kazakh society's nomadic life of the contract, was caused in accordance with the requirements of the developing animal husbandry. Kazakh steppes into Russia in the field is unknown to the public until the passage of all types of cancer into contracts, to adapt to the requirements of the country's economy.

Agreement with the Kazakh steppes, you can see a lot of data about the formation and development of the relations. One of the most important of them, the king of Russian travelers and officials records collected in the field is very valuable. XIX centuries norms of the Kazakh steppe custom worked on many expeditions to collect samples. Traditional Kazakh society and legal institutions, including issues related to the contractual relations between the groups. In most cases, these records Kazakh customs rights norms and institutions, its structure and system, used in Russia during the same period concepts adapted from the scope of the legislation, Russian *jihangerleri* sought to be based on the same concepts. This is an agreement on the right to Kazakh customs relations can be seen in the system of institutions and norms.

Kazakh customs debt into contractual relations in the system right now, storage, exchange, warranty, security of property, mortgage, deed of gift, stability, etc. Conditions were developed. This is understandable, after all, of course, is reflected in the writings of Russian concepts in the period. These contracts are for the most part, Kazakh society has been used centuries later. The main influencing factor, as stated above, is a consequence of the colonization of Russian.

Kazakh society contracts was more extensive information about S. Ualikhanov, N. Gordekova, A.I. Levshina as reflected in the writings of Russian scientists. They Kazakh congregation and conditions of the system to be regulated by the state, its value meaning, types and forms, as well as property of the estate because it is an object of this relationship is only visible in character evidence. In 1886 statistics collected by the Committee of Families of the Kazakh customary rights materials Rome and Russia Empires of movable and immovable property were not. Nomadic way of life based on the value of the animal. Therefore, cattle and other property that has been allocated. Kyrgyzstan cattle wealth, and the rest of movable and immovable property. These documents give is to find the property of the Kyrgyz relations inherited Conditions are based on the facts and legal transactions. Among the most frequent of these can be seen: 1) by way of inheritance, that is their heritage; 2) changes in income, that is good; 3) the angle of animals, ie civil transactions (trades, the god of lightning, lease) [3, p. 464]. In addition, the Kazakh customary right of property as a basis for the rights to have a clear *qaralğandıǵı* contract was drawn up on the basis of the principle of freedom, and they will see that the true and executed by an appropriate basis.

Provisions of the agreement with the traditional Kazakh society relations and analyze the types of institutions, the Kazakh society of wealthy people hire to do, ie, mercenaries are widely developed. In other words, it is important that the individual

contract of employment contract. Such a contract must comply with the following requirements: "If a person entered into between him employment agreement, both dedicated members of the family, the hiring shall be effective as soon as the agreement took place between them. If one of the contracting parties - unselected member of the family member of the family, at the conclusion of the individual employment should be requested permission from the head of the family. The father is entitled to cast in the service or employees of his son, the adult is not selected, with his consent, and even against the will of the minor, and thus concluded an agreement shall be considered valid. However, minor son of his father can give to employees or service only on the condition that his son passed this for 8 years" [4, p. 408]. The maximum term of this contract includes a one-year period of time. In coordination with the requirements of the contract, the parties can introduce other problems. Person so employed in accordance with the agreement, the owner is required to perform all tasks. Mostly the contract the employer has in their family members, children of his employment. There is one particular aspect of the agreement, it does not dominated by a rigid requirement of the agreement. Mostly, this is the vision of the contracts with each other everlasting care. Such contracts are verbal.

Another type of contract is subject to the loan contract. Whole of the loan contract is not broken is one of the traditional Kazakh society, underdeveloped conditions. This condition is unpredictable, the rapid development of the country, the part of Russia, the boom in relation to the money involved. Of course, because of the location of Kazakh nine road network, the determination is in the middle of the Great Silk Road, was held in the trading relations. Trade who is also well-known that there would be a problem loan. Mostly Kazakhs complaint was under review to complete its debt. Loan terms: "The subject of the loan may be all movable property, including money. The lender is prohibited to utter any increase was. If the money or property loan is not specifically stated, what values should be repaid, the return shall be uniform with the obtained values and the corresponding in quality" [4, p. 409-410]. Loan agreement, of course, the traditional Kazakh society is not clearly defined time, however, the writings of the Russian loan agreement will be one of the annual amount of time jasalatındıǵı. Mostly, debt, to be carried out after the fall of Kazakh society livestock census. In some cases, the substance required for the granting of a loan returns, ie, a specific type of animal, age, mutual as may be agreed. In terms of developing a wide range of Kazakh society and collateral agent, using even if from time to time. Basically, all movable property subject to the pledge. Of course the traditional Kazakh society that has already been

recognized by the specifics of the agreement and its implementation. This condition of the guarantee period, aid implementation and use of the term of the contract, there was a completely different character. The requirement of the pledged aid has the following features: "If the mortgagee before the appointed time to sell or otherwise alienate the mortgaged property he loses the right to receive principal and, in addition, mortgagors must pay property value assessment, and if the sale was generated more, all the proceeds" [4, p. 410-411]. In agreement with the traditional Kazakh society relations is another type of contracts used, keeping it is now. This contract is a contract giving the traditional Kazakh society was also called. English said: "stability, do not do against fraud," he said. The terms and conditions of the agreement are as follows: "The subject of the contract of storage and luggage can be any movable property, including money and acts. Contract storage and luggage have a contract free. However, if the guardian or inspector incurred expenses caused by the need to safeguard the property entrusted to them, you are entitled to compensation from the owner or borrower in the amount of expenses incurred. Certain limitations on the duration of the contract and on the storage is not found on the term of the contract is determined by the load condition and signed by the designated recipient snap" [4, p. 411]. Many such conditions as to leave his country, people who have temporarily moved to the other side of the property owned by a relative of the rest of the country was left hostages cherish the source. The man then left imperative, for some reason the review, which he returned. Amanat Institute under after Russia, has become one of the character of the institutions of international law. Amanat is a type of insurance: "The guarantee is allowed in all contracts.

Adoption or adoption of a guarantee given person depends on the discretion of the parties. The remuneration for the guarantee is not intended, unless it is specifically stated in the transaction" [4, p. 412]. In agreement with the Kazakh society relations is the most advanced of the exchange: "The contract of barter is made actual transmission Contracting Parties shall exchange of movable property when the assessment made by them. Termination of swap transactions is permitted only if one of the parties hid the former when the transaction significant deficiencies exchanged property. Deadline for the termination of the transaction is not exactly set" [4, p. 413-414].

Traditional Kazakh society exchange that are often household items. At the same time, many in the Kazakh stock exchange has been carried out. This field is the need of the business.

Purchase and sale agreement centuries Kazakh society of the ancient center of the Turkic khanate, Karahan period used to represent the state. Then, under this condition Russia began to develop rapidly in the past. Russia built a fortress fairs are organized

every year in the major cities of Kazakhstan. That there was a lot of fairs purchase and sale. Purchase and sale agreement with the following requirements: "Purchase - the sale transaction shall be effective from the moment the parties have struck each other's hands. The seller must specify the buyer or known as the master, deficiencies or sold property must notify the buyer of the need to carefully examine the purchase, stating that he resigns from liability in case of discovery of defects in the sold after the transaction" [4, p. 415-416]. Of course, such a requirement, for the most part remained in Kazakh society is not possible to say that. One of the conditions for a wide range of traditional Kazakh society developed, is a condition of the gift. Different things can give as a gift. Made no such things as a gift, which was inherited from his ancestors. Tell the child and the child is not affected. In some cases, that torkindep girl and a gift. He wrote: Father must make his married daughter, came to him, as usual, during the first 5 children of marriage, for the rite "torkin demek" – a gift in the amount of less established by the preceding article, or not received any gifts at all, has the right to require such or the difference" [4, p. 417-418].

Kazakh customs contractual relations in the right gift was one of the main institutes. Which is the gift of ancient epochs to come to an agreement with the interstate relations between man and man, the gift of respect, is the main instrument for understanding. A gift of traditional Kazakh society is so widespread of Kazakhs who gives himself a man of honor, to be entered under the name and walk. Kazakh society gift widespread of Russian authorities did not accept. Makovetskiy P.M. his Kazakh customs and materials related to the right to work says: "Giving the Kirghiz development; not in their lives any solemn occasion, which is not accompanied by more or less significant, mandatory gifts, and besides, there are custom, well-defined legal relationship, the essence of which is reduced to the obligation to and the right to receive gifts. On many obligatory gifts given by at courtship and wedding, mentioned above, and there observed that, according to the Kyrgyz, most wedding can take place without the payment of dowry than without gifts. The last of the gifts to give on the occasion of the wedding, it is considered "torkindeu", a gift given by the father of the bride groom at the entrance to the village Her husband. This gift is not necessary. The groom's father can not give "torkindeu" and no one has the right to demand it does not" [3, p. 357.]. Russian records are often stored in the data related to marriage, family relations. According to the above, the author of the gift to the family level features of forgotten. Mostly gift for Kazakh kyz uzaty, God's face in the implementation of the tradition. Kudalik gift features the following: "Among the individual binding between

relatives gifts, belongs gifts, father married daughter makes each visit her parental village and gifts given by the daughter of parents when they come to the village s husband. Similar to the previous, optional gift grandson of trust during his visit to his grandfather. If it were my grandfather in the first three visits gave nothing, the grandson of the property can take the first, that he likes, and on such a complaint will not be respecting the seizure, because the seized thing entered as the grandson stayed. When visiting honorary Kyrgyz each other, especially if the visit unexpectedly, be sure to also give a gift to enliven the true cost of a guest" [3, p. 358].

Kazakh is the object of the gift. Donation of the various precious things, the needs of the home, which was the property. Kazakh gift to one another, is another feature of the way of a gift. He called at the discretion of the Kazakh customs vascular institute. Cardiovascular Institute of the ancient epochs, which developed one of the institutions. Tamırlık the facts noted above P.M. Makovetskiy describes the following: "But most remarkable gifts, makes Tamyr, ie friends, friendship concluded between themselves, for the most part solely for the exchange of gifts.

In origin, tamyrstvo dates back to antiquity, to the days when the Kirgiz, roaming closer to Central Asia, came in constant collision, as with other tribes, and among them, and when one is trying to create for itself a strong position through the acquisition of possible a large number of friends who are obliged to protect tamyr under the condition of reciprocity. With pacification steppe, with placement of a civil order gradually eliminates the need for the old bond and drevnyago tamyrstva are only some remnants have lost previous practical sense. Currently, there are three kinds of tamyrstva: The strongest link is friendship, connecting with each other dose-Tamir, i.e. friends for ever. Is dose-tamyrstvo by hug topless "Sash Taskan" or shake each other for high palets-"barmak Taskan bonds." Doses - Tamir obliged to help his friend, he can take him without asking anything he pleases and no settlements between friends are not supposed to. During the existence of this friendship is not defined; it goes from fathers to sons for as long as the son of one of Tamir not betrothed daughter of another for himself. In courtship, as well as in the things demanded Tamir should not deny other. Currently dose-tamyrstvo very rare and mostly between the elderly" [3, p. 358]. Tamırlık see that there are several levels in the Kazakh. Tamırlık second level: "The second degree is syuek-tamirlik, i.e. bone friendship ties between the Swat and does not require any special rituals, other than those described above. Finally the lowest, very common form is a verbal friendship (Aus-Tamyr). After some time after the conclusion of tamirlik verbal, as friend send to a friend a gift, and then, after a few months or a year he gets

the equivalent thing called "chopping". If one of the Tamyr, to make a gift, do not get in return equivalent things, or if any of them other benefits in the event of an accident, such as the payment of Kuna, mastered memorial services, etc. special gift - "Gil", the case usually goes to court biys that its decision to make the wrong friend to pay. With some respectful Kyrgyz now to tamirlik between Swat flatter that suit sets really strong bond, "Su suzelmeyde, suek uzelmeyde", ie water does not tsereditsya (without sediment), the bone is not disconnected. Verbal same friendship is not popular. On a man who has a lot of Tamir, seen as vetrennika who can not appreciate the friends of his property: "Tamir Tube dhows kurdas Tube Dzhau", i.e. Tamir will end the dispute, peers will end hostility" [3, p. 359]. Vascular Kazakh society is always the center of attention of the jıqpaytın mutual respect is the basis for tolling.

Institute Kazakh steppes is very popular as a gift. He was at various stages of life: racing won the competition "competition"; and people who trade "market"; The person who got this new thing "Obviously"; friends moved to a new home "erulik"; resolve the dispute successful dance "satal"; Before coming into the girl made up "collars" the worst; Scouting the person who "sauga" requests, etc. numerous gift agreements. Presented substance (cattle, real estate, etc.) will not be refunded. But one of the parties responsible for the prize of gift giving.

Gifts to other types of contract. For example, the daughter of the family has transferred its first 5 years in the torkindeu of all property in the amount of 5% to 10% of the family, "torkindemek" shall receive a reward. But her daughter has the right to claim this prize.

Any donation is a reflection of the respect darxandıqtıñ. At the same time, by the same person, or a donation will be able to see the specifics of the hospitality of the country.

Finally the right to say that the traditional Kazakh system has long been one of the main institutions that gift. Gift Kazakh relations in the contract, that is the gift that recruiters will be forced out by the Kazakh hospitality institute.

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